

GEO Health Community of Practice

Air Quality, Wildfires, and Respiratory Health Work Group

White Paper

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The GEO Health Community of Practice (CoP)'s [Air Quality, Wildfires, and Respiratory Health Work Group](#) aims to identify and disseminate recent progress in air quality applications of Earth observations (EO) to advance respiratory health management and decision-making as it is impacted by air quality. These EO applications include forecasting and early warning for poor air quality, observations of air quality and its drivers using satellite remote sensing, and investigations of the impacts of air quality on human, animal, and ecosystem health through combinations of EO with other environmental data. The activities of this work group support the One Health approach by recognizing that air quality issues represent a key intersection of human, animal, and environmental health.

Poor air quality has a direct negative impact on human health, contributing to an estimated one in nine deaths globally (HEI, 2024). Poor environmental health can exacerbate wildfires and dust storms, leading to reduced air quality. Animals are likewise impacted by poor air quality (ECCC, 2012; Manisalidis et al., 2020), and human agricultural practices involving animals also have their own air quality impacts (Domingo et al., 2021). Air pollution further impacts the environment, including ecosystems and vegetation, through direct effects and atmospheric deposition (Stevens et al., 2020; Pavlovic et al., 2023). Furthermore, the combined effects of exposures from multiple sources and through multiple pathways (e.g., the compounding effects of high heat and poor air quality on human health, or the indirect effects of air quality on water quality via deposition and runoff) lead to complex, interconnected, and interdependent impacts which can only be captured through a One Health approach (e.g., Kortenkamp and Faust, 2018).

By advancing best practices for the monitoring of air quality using EO data on pollutants like particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide, and ozone, the Work Group not only supports the prediction of health and environmental risks due to these factors, but also assists in building capacity among stakeholders. With the adoption of the One Health approach, this information can be used to warn vulnerable populations and advocate for cleaner air policies. The long-term climate impact and short-term human health co-benefits of air pollution reduction are often cited to serve as robust evidence for policy development (e.g., Mudu et al., 2023).

Opportunities for Satellite EO Data in Air Quality and Respiratory Health

In-situ observations of the concentrations of key pollutants by ground-based regulatory air quality monitoring networks are the foundational source of data for understanding and managing air quality (Hasenkopf et al., 2023). However, due to the costs of establishing and maintaining such systems, they are relatively sparse on a global scale, with most regions having less than one monitor per million people for fine particulate matter (also known as PM_{2.5}), a key air quality

indicator (Malings et al., 2024a). This sparsity of in-situ data limits understanding of spatial variability, hinders identification of sources, and obfuscates the link between air pollution and its health burden at the local level.

Satellite EO data can be used to assess regional and global air quality patterns and trends to complement in-situ monitoring (Duncan et al., 2021). The global views offered by satellite EO can help make air quality data accessible for broader global communities, including those in remote areas or those otherwise underserved by surface-based air quality monitoring networks. Furthermore, many satellite EO data sources offer near real-time information, which will allow for early warnings about dust storms, wildfires, or other events that can rapidly degrade air quality. Real-time data can be used to issue targeted advisories to vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, or those with respiratory issues, which can allow them to take precautions during periods of high pollution (O'Dell et al., 2024).

Combining long-term satellite EO data on air quality with health data from local hospitals, researchers can better understand how air pollution impacts public health (Anenberg et al., 2022). Long-term trends can also inform effective air quality regulations (Potts et al., 2021, 2024). Local authorities can use this information to target specific sources of pollution and implement stricter emission controls. For example, by combining air quality data with satellite data on land use and vegetation cover, the Work Group can identify areas where agricultural practices contribute to dust generation, which can offer insight into dust-reducing practices among local farmers.

Finally, use of satellite EO data enables collaboration between multiple disciplines (such as atmospheric science, sociology, human geography, meteorology, epidemiology, environmental sciences, and public policy) by providing information with regional coverage at similar spatiotemporal scales. By bringing these data sets together into a common analysis, air quality (and other issues) can be examined and addressed holistically. This integration can lead to a more comprehensive approach that can improve both the understanding and management of air quality and its impacts on human, animal, and environmental health.

Challenges in using Satellite EO Data in Air Quality and Respiratory Health

In general, use of EO data to monitor and manage air quality is hindered by barriers to data access and interpretation. Data files are large, formats are inconsistent, interpreting retrieval quality information can be complex, and spatial and temporal resolutions do not match user needs and must be re-gridded and averaged, which is technically and computationally challenging. Providing pre-generated datasets in standardized formats, accessible in web-based cloud computing platforms could reduce the technical barriers to data use. Ensuring free and easy access to EO data and free user-friendly tools for interpretation by communities with varying technical backgrounds is a key outstanding need.

Efforts, such as the [NASA Applied Remote Sensing Training Program](#), providing free online lessons in how to apply EO data to address many issues, including air quality, are beginning to address this gap. Language and cultural barriers, as well as skepticism and mistrust of “helicopter” scientists without connections to local communities and their concerns, are additional barriers to applying EO data in practice (Ivey et al., 2022). Inclusive international communities of practice, such as this Work Group, can begin to build trust and lower these barriers. Finally, while many organizations make the EO data they collect publicly available, national air quality monitoring

agencies do not necessarily make in-situ air quality data publicly available, hindering inter-comparisons and combinations of insights from these complementary datasets at a global scale.

While satellite EO can provide information on the presence of pollutants in the atmospheric column, relating these to the surface-level concentrations most directly relevant to air quality requires additional sources of information and can be technically challenging to do. Recent advances are aiming to create flexible, scalable frameworks for such conversions which can be implemented in cloud-computing platforms to increase accessibility for these tools (Malings et al., 2024b). Using satellite EO data to remotely estimate emissions of pollutants is another promising area of work, which can help generate data to guide emissions controls with relatively low latency (Liu et al., 2024). However, more work is needed to make these techniques accessible and usable by regulatory bodies and policy-makers.

While the expansion of EO data has provided unprecedented access to air quality information, data accuracy and applicability often hinge on robust validation processes. Particularly in the Global South, there is a critical need for more validation sites (such as those provided by the [Pandonia](#) and [AERONET](#) networks), especially in urban areas, as it allows for more accurate calibration of satellite data against the complex air quality dynamics typical of densely populated regions. This step would not only enhance the reliability of EO data, but also improve the precision of air quality assessments in areas most affected by pollution yet often underrepresented in global monitoring efforts.

Work Group Activities Promoting One Health Solutions

The Work Group aims to highlight and promote case studies of successful applications of EO data in air quality management. It has involved its own members and has reached out to global experts to host a series of presentations summarizing the current state of science and practice in air quality and its relationship to human, environmental, and animal health. For example, in 2023, the Work Group hosted presentations related to Multi-Angle Imager for Aerosols ([MAIA](#)), NASA's first health-focused mission ([slides](#)), impact of combustion conditions on composition of wildfire emissions (Anderson et al., 2023), connections between environmental health and the air quality impacts of wildfires ([slides](#)), and global data fusion and exposure products for relating air quality and human health impacts (van Donkelaar et al., 2021).

The Work Group is also involved in developing and delivering regionally specific resource guides and training workshops on available EO datasets and analysis techniques. First, in collaboration with the NASA Health and Air Quality Applied Sciences Team ([HAQAST](#)) and [SERVIR](#), the Work Group is updating and adapting a [flowchart](#) to guide users towards satellite EO and derived data products which are applicable to assessing different pollutants in different regions at different spatio-temporal scales. Through this effort, the applicability of the flowchart will be expanded beyond the United States (its current scope) to wider regional and global scales, including information on new global and regional datasets and analysis tools.

Second, Work Group members prepared an introductory workshop on [Satellite-Derived Air Quality Information for the Americas](#), as part of the [AmeriGEO](#) Week 2024, which included an overview of available EO datasets relevant to air quality in Central and South America, case studies of the application of EO data to air quality topics, and free online resources of accessing, visualizing, and analyzing EO data. In the second half of the workshop, participants were given

time to explore these resources on their own, apply them to a case study of interest to them, and share their experiences (including barriers) when finding and applying EO data. Based on participant feedback, the Work Group plans to refine the workshop materials and conduct similar workshops during other regional meetings of health and air quality professionals in the future (e.g., [AfriGEO Symposium](#)). The Work Group plans to expand these workshops by tailoring regionally specific resource guides, involving non-governmental organizations operating in areas and sectors to pass information to their stakeholders, as well as incorporating citizen science initiatives that engage residents to collect ground-based air quality data alongside satellite EO data using low-cost, accessible instruments (WMO et al., 2024). The Work Group also aims at fostering local capacity building in low- and middle-income countries through partnerships with local institutions, including universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, and relevant public agencies.

The Work Group continues to serve as a forum for international engagement between the providers of EO data, including aerospace, remote sensing, and hydro/geo/meteorological agencies, and those using EO data for human and environmental health impact assessment and management, such as environmental and public health agencies. This forum supports holistic assessments of the causes and solutions to air quality and respiratory health issues, underpinning a One Health approach to these problems. It also allows Work Group members to readily identify global data gaps needed to connect air quality with human, environmental, and animal health impacts. A future goal of the Work Group is to create a list of specific recommendations for new EO missions and data products which can address these gaps.

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